

THE METHOD OF PROJECTS IN TEACHING ENGLISH: THE RELATIONSHIP OF STUDY AND PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

With the advancement of modern technologies, information and knowledge play a larger role in all areas of social development. Owning the knowledge in your native tongue is insufficient for the expert. As a result, the activity-based approach to teaching foreign languages is the best way to ensure that the learning process is as relevant to the trainee's potential professional employment as possible. We refer to applying various problem-solving techniques. They are research, search, contested methods, and a project approach that combines all of the aforementioned methods.

Key words: *approach, activity, a method of projects, problematic, differential education, foreign language.*

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan's rapid entry into the world community, integration processes in various spheres of politics, economy, culture, ideology, mixing and displacement of peoples and languages, actualize the problem of intercultural communication, mutual understanding of communication participants belonging to different cultures. These processes require changes in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, solving new problems in the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages. One more significant factor should be kept in mind. With development knowledge-intensive technologies are increasing the role of information and knowledge at all levels and in all spheres of social development. Knowledge and qualifications become priority values in a person's life in an information society. It is necessary, however, to state the gap in the level of training of specialists with higher education and the requirements of society. A modern specialist is a well-educated person in a particular field, with fundamental training, capable of continuous professional development. For a modern specialist, knowledge of at least two foreign languages is a necessary condition for his professionalism, allowing him to work with information, as well as communicate with foreign colleagues. All this involves fundamental and versatile training, requires the

use of new methods and means of training. In our opinion, foreign language teaching should be based on an activity-based approach, which means that the learning process should be maximally it is close to the future professional activity of the student. Working with information in any language requires the formation of certain intellectual skills: the ability to analyze information, select the necessary facts, building them in a logical sequence, the ability to put forward arguments and counterarguments, etc. As a rule, starting to work in a specialty, when communicating with their foreign colleagues, a young specialist is faced with the need to solve problems of theoretical and practical significance that require a clear and clear thought, the ability to formulate this idea orally or written in a foreign language. We believe that the problem of forming a stable motivation to learn foreign languages is solved most successfully if its solution is based on the formation of the need to communicate in a foreign language, which, in turn, presupposes the presence of a certain language environment. This problem is one of the central ones in modern methodology, which opens the way to a genuine optimization of the educational process. Therefore, we believe that the process of learning a foreign language can be effectively actualize by problematizing the educational process using information sources. We are talking about using a number of problematic methods by their nature. This includes research, search, discussion methods, and the project method, which includes all the methods listed above.

LITERATURE REVIEW METHODOLOGY

If we talk about the method of projects, it should be noted that in the XIX - early XX century. This direction of problem methods was developed by J. Dewey (1859-1952). Paying special attention to the need for the formation of reflex thinking, he argued that thinking is the solution of problems, i.e. "problem solving" (1909). He identified 5 stages of the formation of reflective thinking: 1) consideration of all possible solutions or assumptions; 2) awareness of the difficulty and formulation of the problem to be solved; 3) nomination assumptions as a hypothesis that determines the direction of observation and the collection of facts; 4) argumentation and putting in order the discovered facts; 5) practical or imaginary verification of the correctness of the hypotheses put forward. The project method is based on methods of activating learning, research methods. [1] E.S.Polat proposed the definition of this method: "The project method involves a certain set of educational and cognitive techniques and actions of trainees that allow solving a particular problem as a result of independent cognitive actions and involving the presentation of these results in the form of a specific product of activity. The project method is from the field of didactics, private methods, if it is used in the framework of a certain subject. Method is a didactic category. This

is a set of techniques, operations of mastering a certain area of practical or theoretical knowledge, a particular activity. This is the way of cognition, the way of organizing the process of cognition. Therefore, if we are talking about the method of projects, we mean exactly the way to achieve the didactic goal through the detailed development of the problem (technology), which should end with a very real, tangible practical result, framed in one way or another.”[6] Today, the project method is being used again, but in an updated form. It can be considered an effective stage in the formation of critical thinking. The project differs from other problematic methods in that, as a result of certain search, research, and creative activity, students not only come to a solution to the problem, but also create a concrete real product that shows the ability and ability to apply the results obtained in practice when creating this product. In the process of working on by the project, students independently (individually or, more often, in small groups), without the help of a teacher or with minimal help, isolate a problem from a problematic situation, dissect it into subproblems, put forward hypotheses for their solutions, investigate subproblems and connections between them, and then return to the main problem and suggest ways to solve it. During the defense of the project, a broad discussion in English of the proposed solutions, opposition, discussion is provided. Therefore, the project participants are required to the ability to argue one’s point of view, to put forward counterarguments to opponents, to support a discussion, to come to a compromise. The project method allows students to form the skills of independent research in a given area, which will help them to further implement more complex projects in their professional activities. The method of projects in the teaching of foreign languages and social disciplines is a multi-level training, reflecting the specifics of the differentiation of training, as well as a way to achieve a didactic goal through a detailed study of the problem. To achieve as a practical result, it is necessary to teach students to think independently; to find and solve problems, attracting knowledge from different fields for this purpose. The project approach in the course of work not only helps to consolidate the knowledge and skills acquired in the disciplines, but also by providing appropriate situations, develop the ability to apply knowledge, and often the knowledge students need to work on a project spurs the development of interest in other sciences. [5]. Projects designed for language learning have both common to all projects features and distinctive features, among which the main ones are the following:

- the use of language in situations as close as possible to the conditions of real communication;
- emphasis on independent work of students (individual and group);

- choosing a topic that is of great interest to students and is directly related to the conditions in which the project is being carried out;
- selection of language material, types of tasks and sequence of work in accordance with the theme and purpose of the project;
- visual representation of the result.

In the language teaching environment, we distinguish three types of projects:

1. A group project in which "research is conducted by the whole group, and each student studies a certain aspect of the chosen topic."
2. A mini-study consisting of conducting an "individual sociological survey using questionnaires and interviews".
3. A project based on working with literature, implying "selective reading on a topic of interest to the student" and suitable for individual work.

A personally significant, motivated speech utterance of the listener in the project activity is the main condition that serves as the best prerequisite formation of speech activity of speaking. In the process of project activity, the listener is given the opportunity to express their own opinions, feelings, and share experiences. For example: the introduction of new lexical material (the device of the car in English) in groups for beginners takes place in the form of a blitz survey: which brand of car do you like, which do not like and why? After all, each of us has certain associations with a particular topic. The discussion is always accompanied by a surge of emotions among the listeners. Teamwork significantly increases the motivation of listeners and the opportunity to exchange ideas and help each other. To consolidate the material within the phonetic course, we proposed the game "Association". The group is divided into 2 teams. The first team receives a list of words to be guessed by the second team (lexical material for the English language course) and a box with objects- associations. So, guess the first word (present- to present): the first command demonstrates the object-association (piston—a piston) and provides information about the number of letters and sounds (the word an engine has 6 letters and 6 sounds), etc. Consequently, we see that in the process of active mental foreign language speech activity during project work, various kinds of associations arise between a foreign language and the listener's own world, which contributes to the development of communicative competence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thus, it allows you to implement interdisciplinary connections in teaching a foreign language, expand the "narrow space" of communication in the audience, make a broad reliance on practical activities typical for students of each age group groups. Secondly, working on a project is a creative process. Students on their own or under

the guidance of the teacher, they are searching for a solution to a problem that is personally significant for them. This requires students to independently transfer knowledge, skills and abilities into a new context of their use. Consequently, students develop creative competence as an indicator of communicative proficiency in a foreign language. Thirdly, during the implementation of the project, the student is active, he shows creative interest and is not a passive executor of the teacher's will. The project work allows us to exclude the formal nature of the study students of the language (on the principle of "need to know") and activates their interaction to achieve a practical result of language learning. Fourth, the project fundamentally changes the functional responsibilities of the student and the teacher. The first one actively participates in the selection, organization and design of the content of foreign language teaching and a specific lesson; the second one acts as a consultant, assistant, and participant in the game. Students demonstrate a higher degree of involvement in the learning process, motivation and joy they are more confident in themselves, they have a higher level of self-esteem, as well as a degree of trust in the teacher and classmates. The use of project methodology in teaching contributes to improving the effectiveness of mastering a foreign language. Such an organization of work is a means of motivating students and increasing the effectiveness of their academic work. The project method makes it possible to maximize individualization and differentiation of learning, which is expressed in providing the student with conditions for working on feasible software the volume and complexity of the task at an individual pace, which creates equal opportunities for the personal growth of all students, the realization of the potential inherent in nature. We have attempted to develop a methodology for organizing and conducting project activities of students at the initial and secondary stages of teaching foreign languages at a university in order to form a communicative foreign language competence. The specifics of the organization of students' project activities in foreign language classes and after-school hours are determined. A system of tasks has been developed to prepare for the project activities and for its implementation. Another real possibility of implementing interdisciplinary connections in teaching foreign languages is shown.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that participation in the project was very useful for students, as it allowed them to really get involved in future professional activities and get an idea of what aspects of the specialty language will be in demand in it. Of course, we do not consider the project method as the main one that determines the strategy of teaching foreign languages, claiming to displace other methods and types of educational activities. The project method is just one of the methods that adequately

reflects a personality-oriented approach that can be effectively used on various stages of training in combination with other methods. However, with its competent use, the project method contributes to a more effective solution of methodological tasks and tasks of developing learning related to the formation of pragmatic competence, the formation of intellectual skills to work with information, the formation and improvement of socio-cultural competence, individualization and differentiation of the learning process, the formation of sustainable motivation of learning.

REFERENCES:

1. Dewey J. Psychology and pedagogy of thinking. Berlin. 1922. – 254 p.
2. Zimnaya I.A. Project methodology of teaching English// Foreign languages at school. 1991. No. 3. pp. 91-97.
3. Zimnaya I.A. Key competencies – new paradigms of the result of education// Higher education today. 2003. No.5. pp. 34- 42.
4. Kopylova V.V. Methodology of project work in English lessons language. M., 2003. – 185 p.
5. Pobokova O.A., Nemchenko A.A. New technologies in language teaching: project work// New communication opportunities: achievements linguistics, technologies and methods of teaching languages. Irkutsk, 2003. pp. 49-55.
6. Polat E.S. Theoretical foundations of the compilation and use of a system of foreign language teaching tools for secondary schools. Abstract. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. M., 1989.
7. Polat E.S., Bukharkina M.Yu., Moiseev M.V., Petrova A.E. New pedagogical and information technologies in the education system. M.: Academy. 2005. 272 p.
8. Babadjanova N.X. (2023). IMPLEMENTATION OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING FOR TEACHING ENGLISH - ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 122(06), 38-40
9. Baisov, A.S. (2021). DEFINING THE ROLE OF TANDEM METHOD IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE. - ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 5 (97),450-452.
10. Baisov, A.S. (2023). The SIGNIFICANCE OF EXTRACURRICULAR EXERCISES IN CREATING DIALECT ABILITIES OF ESP LEARNERS.- ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 122 (06), 35-37
11. Babadjanova N.X., Babajanova K.I. (2023) CHALLENGES AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS OF TEACHING ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN UZBEK CLASSES.- Academic Research in Educational Sciences, 4(3),459-465
12. Babadjanova N., Baisov A. (2022) THE IMPORTANCE OF THE «QUEST» TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 6(110), 333-35.